

Supplementary Material

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Redundancy	c (X14)	Labor productivity	X8	China Urban Statistical Yearbook	billion CNY / 10,000 people	https://data.cnki.net/yearBook/single?id=N2025020156&pinyinCode=YZGCA
		Per capita road area	X9	China Urban Construction Statistical Yearbook	m ² /person	https://data.cnki.net/yearBook/single?id=N2023110029&pinyinCode=YCJTJ
		Proportion of water-related personnel	X10	China Urban Statistical Yearbook	%	https://data.cnki.net/yearBook/single?id=N2025020156&pinyinCode=YZGCA
		Proportion of land for logistics and warehousing	X11	China Urban Construction Statistical Yearbook	%	https://data.cnki.net/yearBook/single?id=N2023110029&pinyinCode=YCJTJ
Resourcefulness	d	Fixed value = 1	/	References	/	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0951832018313152

2 Weight calculation method

Criteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation (CRITIC) is an objective weighting method that determines indicator weights by jointly considering contrast intensity (i.e., variability) and conflict (i.e., inter-indicator correlation) (Diakoulaki et al. 1995). The algorithmic procedure is outlined as follows.

(1) Data normalization

The original indicator matrix is normalized by distinguishing between positive and negative indicators to eliminate the influence of scale. Suppose there are n cities and m indicators; the normalized matrix is denoted as $X = [x_{ij}]_{n \times m}$.

(2) Computation of contrast intensity (standard deviation)

The standard deviation σ_j of each indicator is calculated to reflect the degree of dispersion (Eq. S1). A larger σ_j indicates a stronger discriminative ability of the indicator in the evaluation system.

$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)^2}, \quad j=1,2,\dots,m \quad (\text{S1})$$

(3) Computation of conflict (correlation coefficient)

The Pearson correlation coefficient matrix $R = [r_{jk}]_{m \times m}$ is computed to assess

redundancy among indicators (**Eq. S2**). The conflict level of an indicator is defined as $1 - r_{jk}$, where a lower correlation implies higher independence.

$$r_{jk} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)(x_{ik} - \bar{x}_k)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (x_{ik} - \bar{x}_k)^2}} \quad (\text{S2})$$

(4) Computation of information content

Each indicator's information content C_j is calculated by integrating its contrast intensity and conflict level (**Eq. S3**). A higher C_j indicates greater contribution to the evaluation system.

$$C_j = \sigma_j \times \sum_{k=1}^m (1 - |r_{jk}|), \quad j=1,2,\dots,m \quad (\text{S3})$$

(5) Computation of weights

The final weight w_j of each indicator is obtained by normalizing its information content (**Eq. S4**).

$$w_j = \frac{C_j}{\sum_{k=1}^m C_k}, \quad j = 1,2,3,\dots,m \quad (\text{S4})$$

Compared to other objective weighting methods such as TOPSIS and the entropy method, CRITIC is particularly suitable for resilience assessment under extreme rainfall scenarios (Han, Wang, et al. 2023; Wu et al. 2024). This is because CRITIC balances indicator variability and redundancy while reducing the influence of multicollinearity. In resilience evaluations, indicators often exhibit strong correlations (e.g., *drainage network density* and *flood control investment ratio* both reflect flood defense capacity). CRITIC accounts for such redundancies by incorporating a correlation matrix into its weighting scheme, automatically reducing the influence of highly correlated variables. Moreover, under extreme rainfall conditions, indicator importance within the CRITIC method depends not only on variation (e.g., the standard deviation of the composite *Prep_shock* index (X1) across cities, reflecting differences in the calculated risk these cities face due to the combination of extreme rainfall hazard intensity, capital exposure, and event rarity considered in the index) but also on independence (e.g., total factor productivity complements labor productivity), both of which are captured by the CRITIC method.

3 Method for calculating extreme rainfall shock

(1) Threshold filtering of extreme rainfall events

Spatiotemporal grid cells that satisfy both rainfall intensity and exceedance probability thresholds are identified (Eq. S5). Let Ω denote the set of grid cells within city i at time t that simultaneously experience a rainfall event and have a historical probability of rainfall ≥ 50 mm greater than or equal to 0.01. Here, $HR_Intensity^{grid,t}$ is the rainfall intensity of grid g at time t , and $Prob_gte50^{grid}$ is the exceedance probability of ≥ 50 mm daily rainfall based on historical data (China, 0.1° resolution, 1961–2022).

$$\Omega = \{(grid,t) | HR_Intensity^{grid,t} \geq 50\text{mm}, Prob_gte50^{grid} > 0.01\} \quad (S5)$$

(2) Rainfall intensity normalization

Observed rainfall intensities are normalized to a $[0,1]$ scale to ensure comparability (Eq. S6), where $Max_Intensity^{grid,historical}$ is the historical maximum rainfall intensity for grid.

$$N_Intensity^{grid,t} = \frac{HR_Intensity^{grid,t}}{Max_Intensity^{grid,historical}} \quad (S6)$$

(3) Historical probability normalization

To highlight the extremity of rare events, rainfall observations are weighted by the inverse of their historical exceedance probability (Eq. S7). Lower-probability events are assigned higher weights.

$$W_Event^{grid} = \frac{1}{Prob_gte50^{grid}} \quad (S7)$$

(4) Capital exposure calculation

The exposed capital stock proportion under extreme rainfall is quantified (Eq. S8), where $Capital_shock^{grid,t}$ represents the capital stock in affected grid cells, and $Capital^{city,t}$ is the total capital stock of the city.

$$E_Capital^{grid,t} = \frac{Capital_shock^{grid,t}}{Capital^{city,t}} \quad (S8)$$

(5) Spatial aggregation

The overall spatial impact of a rainfall event is calculated by aggregating the adjusted intensity and probability across all qualifying grid cells (Eq. S9).

$$S_shock^t = \sum_{grid \in \Omega} (N_Intensity^{grid,t} \times W_Event^{grid} \times E_Capital^{grid,t}) \quad (S9)$$

(6) Temporal aggregation

The annual cumulative shock intensity from 2019 to 2022 is then computed for each city (**Eq. S10**).

$$Prep_shock = \sum_{t=365}^{t_{shock}} S_shock^t \quad (S10)$$

4 Attribution method

4.1 Machine Learning modeling

4.1.1 RF

Random Forest (RF) is an ensemble decision tree model that combines bagging and feature randomization strategies (Gu et al. 2025). For a dataset with n samples and m features, each decision tree is trained on a bootstrap sample, and at each split, k features ($k \leq m$) are randomly selected for node optimization. The final prediction \hat{y}_i for sample i is obtained by averaging the predictions of all T trees (**Eq. S11**):

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_i) \quad (S11)$$

Here, $f_t(x_i)$ denotes the prediction function of the t -th decision tree. RF is robust against overfitting and is well-suited for high-dimensional data, particularly in cases with multicollinearity among variables (e.g., drainage network density and flood control investment ratio).

4.1.2 Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM)

EBM is a "glass-box" model that achieves interpretability through gradient boosting and additive feature interaction (Nori et al. 2019). The model takes the form shown in **Eq. S12**.

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{j=1}^m f_j(x_{ij}) + \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k>j}^m f_{jk}(x_{ij}, x_{ik}) + \epsilon_i \quad (S12)$$

Here, $f_j(x_{ij})$ represents the shape function for individual features, and $f_{jk}(x_{ij}, x_{ik})$ denotes the pairwise interaction terms. EBM directly outputs feature importance scores (e.g., the marginal contribution of drainage network density to

resilience recovery), making it suitable for policy prioritization analysis.

4.1.3 XGBoost

XGBoost mitigates overfitting by introducing regularization into gradient-boosted decision trees. Its objective function consists of a loss term (\mathcal{L}) and a regularization term that penalizes model complexity (Ω) (Eq. S13).

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{t=1}^T \Omega(f_t), \quad \Omega(f_t) = \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \|w\|^2 \quad (\text{S13})$$

Here, T is the number of leaf nodes, w is the leaf weight, and γ and λ are regularization parameters. XGBoost excels at capturing complex nonlinear patterns, such as the threshold effect of infrastructure redundancy on recovery speed.

Table S2 Hyperparameter search space and optimal values for each model.

Model	Hyperparameter	Search space / Range	Optimal value (for Resilience)	Optimal value (for Recovery time)
Random Forest	n_estimators	Integer: [100, 500)	234	234
	max_depth	Integer: [5, 30)	29	29
	max_features	Categorical: ['sqrt', 'log2']	sqrt'	sqrt'
	min_samples_split	Integer: [2, 10)	4	4
	min_samples_leaf	Integer: [1, 5)	1	1
XGBoost	n_estimators	Integer: [100, 500)	466	466
	learning_rate	Float: [0.011, 0.111)	0.0955	0.0955
	max_depth	Integer: [3, 5)	3	3
	min_child_weight	Integer: [15, 25)	16	16
	subsample	Float: [0.7, 0.85)	0.8243	0.8243
	colsample_bytree	Float: [0.3, 0.8)	0.7806	0.7806
EBM	max_rounds	Integer: [100, 500)	379	341
	max_bins	Integer: [30, 100)	82	43
	learning_rate	Float: [0.001, 0.011)	0.0094	0.0104

4.2 Attribution Methods

4.2.1 SHAP interpretation (XGBoost)

Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) is a game-theoretic approach that

quantifies the contribution of each feature to a model prediction ((Meddage et al. 2022) et al., 2022). The Shapley value ϕ_j for feature j is computed as follows (Eq. S14).

$$\phi_j = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{j\}} \frac{|S|!(|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f(S \cup \{j\}) - f(S)] \quad (\text{S14})$$

Where F is the set of all features, S is a subset that does not include j , and $f(S)$ is the model output with features in S . SHAP values can reveal nonlinear main effects, such as the diminishing marginal returns of drainage network density.

4.2.2 Intrinsic attribution (EBM)

EBM provides direct outputs of feature importance scores ($\text{Importance}_j = \mathbb{E}[|f_j(x_j)|]$) and interaction strengths ($\text{Interaction}_{jk} = \mathbb{E}[|f_{jk}(x_j, x_k)|]$) through its additive structure, offering intuitive guidance for resilience enhancement strategies.

4.2.3 Interaction effect analysis

A three-level full factorial design is employed to systematically test interaction effects among resilience dimensions (Smucker et al. 2019). Taking robustness (a), rapidity (b), and redundancy (c) as an example, the general form of the model is given in Eq. S15, with interaction effects estimated via analysis of variance (ANOVA).

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_a a + \beta_b b + \beta_c c + \beta_{ab} ab + \beta_{ac} ac + \beta_{bc} bc + \beta_{abc} abc + \epsilon \quad (\text{S15})$$

5 Urban classification

Table S3 Classification of Chinese cities by scale and corresponding standards.

City Scale	City Scale Standards (URP: Urban Resident Population)
Mega City	URP \geq 10 million
Super Large City	5 million $<$ URP \leq 10 million
Large City	1 million $<$ URP \leq 5 million
Medium City	0.5 million $<$ URP \leq 1 million
Small City	URP \leq 0.5 million

The city scale classification standard adopted in this study is based on the official policy issued by the People's Republic of China on November 21, 2014, titled "*Notice on Adjusting the Standards for Urban Scale Classification.*" According to this guideline, cities are classified into five categories—Small, Medium, Large, Super Large, and Mega Cities—based on the resident population within built-up urban areas (Table S3).

In this context, "urban population" refers to the permanent population residing in built-up areas, which include zones under the jurisdiction of residents' committees connected to the actual construction of municipal districts or non-district-level cities, excluding towns and rural areas.

Table S4 Scope of China's geographical regions

Region	Geographical scope
North	Beijing, Tianjin, Hebei, Shanxi, Shandong, Inner Mongolia
Northeast	Liaoning, Jilin, Heilongjiang
East	Shanghai, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, Anhui, Fujian, Jiangxi, Shandong
Central South	Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Guangdong, Guangxi, Hainan
Southwest	Chongqing, Sichuan, Guizhou, Yunnan, Tibet
Northwest	Shanxi, Gansu, Ningxia, Xinjiang

In this study, China is divided into six major geographical regions based on conventional administrative and economic groupings (**Table S4**). This regional classification reflects both spatial proximity and shared climatic, economic, and administrative characteristics.

6 Statistical analysis of city classification

Fig. S1 The proportion of cities within each level after classification using the natural breaks (Jenks) method.

Fig. S2 Resilience statistics by city scale and region

Fig. S3 Recovery time statistics by city scale and region

7 City statistics by quadrant

Fig. S4 Ternary plot of multi-year averages (2019–2022)

Fig. S5 Proportion of cities in each quadrant by city scale

Fig. S6 Proportion of cities in each quadrant by region

Table S5 Cities located in quadrant IV of the ternary plots from 2019 to 2022 and multi-year averages

Quadrant	2019	2020	2021	2022	Multi-year average
IV	Guilin	#N/A	#N/A	Guilin	Guilin
IV	Jinzhou	Jinzhou	Jinzhou	#N/A	Jinzhou
IV	Meizhou	Meizhou	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
IV	Huludao	Huludao	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
IV	Dazhou	#N/A	Dazhou	#N/A	Dazhou
IV	Zhoukou	#N/A	Zhoukou	#N/A	Zhoukou
IV	Nanyang	#N/A	Nanyang	Nanyang	Nanyang
IV	Neijiang	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
IV	Hegang	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
IV	Shangqiu	Shangqiu	Shangqiu	Shangqiu	Shangqiu

IV	Xinyang	Xinyang	Xinyang	Xinyang	Xinyang
IV	Linfen	#N/A	Linfen	#N/A	#N/A
IV	Lvliang	#N/A	Lvliang	Lvliang	Lvliang
IV	Tieling	#N/A	#N/A	Tieling	Tieling
IV	Liaoyuan	Liaoyuan	#N/A	Liaoyuan	Liaoyuan
IV	Heihe	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
IV	Zhumadian	Zhumadian	Zhumadian	Zhumadian	Zhumadian
IV	Baicheng	Baicheng	#N/A	Baicheng	Baicheng
IV	Shuangyashan	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	Shuangyashan
IV	Songyuan	Songyuan	Songyuan	Songyuan	Songyuan
IV	Bazhong	#N/A	#N/A	Bazhong	Bazhong
IV	Zhaotong	Zhaotong	Zhaotong	Zhaotong	Zhaotong
IV	Baoshan	Baoshan	Baoshan	#N/A	Baoshan

8 ANOVA analysis

Table S6 ANOVA results of the interaction effects between resilience and the three parameters

Effect	SS	df	MS	F	p
X12 (a)	4.7923	2	2.3961	355.1211	0.0000
X13 (b)	0.9345	2	0.4672	69.2490	0.0000
X14 (c)	7.7943	2	3.8971	577.5785	0.0000
X12*X13 (ab)	0.0750	4	0.0187	2.7775	0.0260
X12*X14 (ac)	0.8715	4	0.2179	32.2899	0.0000
X13*X14 (bc)	0.3776	4	0.0944	13.9890	0.0000
X12*X13*X14 (abc)	0.0738	8	0.0092	1.3681	0.2067
Error	5.6273	834	0.0067	-	-

Table S7 ANOVA results of the interaction effects between recovery time and the three parameters

Effect	SS	df	MS	F	p
X12 (a)	0.2714	2	0.1357	25.1366	0.0000
X13 (b)	3.8173	2	1.9086	353.5010	0.0000
X14 (c)	6.5519	2	3.2759	606.7390	0.0000
X12*X13 (ab)	0.1033	4	0.0258	4.7817	0.0008
X12*X14 (ac)	0.2083	4	0.0521	9.6457	0.0000
X13*X14 (bc)	0.6940	4	0.1735	32.1322	0.0000
X12*X13*X14 (abc)	0.2176	8	0.0272	5.0379	0.0000
Error	4.5030	834	0.0054	-	-

9 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and permutation feature importance analysis

Table S8 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for model indicators

Feature	VIF
X1	2.55
X2	3.50
X3	2.89
X4	2.38
X5	3.27
X6	2.32
X7	3.40
X8	2.22
X9	2.29
X10	1.30
X11	1.39
X12	6.15
X13	7.20
X14	3.85
const	1424.64

Table S9 Permutation feature importance for resilience prediction across different models

Random Forest		EBM		XGBoost	
Feature	Importance	Feature	Importance	Feature	Importance
X14	0.3582	X14	0.5915	X14	0.7014
X12	0.1134	X1	0.2712	X13	0.2470
X1	0.0770	X13	0.1714	X1	0.1876
X2	0.0647	X2	0.0681	X12	0.0975
X9	0.0583	X12	0.0678	X2	0.0519
X13	0.0473	X9	0.0509	X9	0.0261
X8	0.0161	X3	0.0220	X8	0.0166
X3	0.0092	X8	0.0096	X3	0.0165
X6	0.0078	X5	0.0054	X5	0.0151
X4	0.0054	X4	0.0048	X4	0.0063
X5	0.0030	X10	0.0029	X6	0.0042
X10	0.0028	X7	0.0009	X10	0.0031
X11	0.0007	X6	0.0002	X7	0.0026
X7	0.0001	X11	-0.0002	X11	0.0026

Table S10 Permutation feature importance for recovery time prediction across different models

Random Forest		EBM		XGBoost	
Feature	Importance	Feature	Importance	Feature	Importance
X14	0.4355	X14	0.6213	X14	0.7134
X13	0.2931	X13	0.3168	X13	0.4734
X8	0.0747	X5	0.0480	X9	0.0275
X9	0.0494	X7	0.0417	X5	0.0211

X5	0.0431	X8	0.0404	X8	0.0207
X7	0.0231	X9	0.0346	X7	0.0164
X10	0.0195	X4	0.0267	X4	0.0149
X4	0.0156	X6	0.0162	X10	0.0134
X2	0.0119	X10	0.0158	X6	0.0062
X6	0.0077	X11	0.0054	X12	0.0050
X12	0.0041	X1	0.0023	X11	0.0019
X3	0.0028	X12	0.0012	X3	0.0001
X11	0.0021	X3	0.0005	X2	-0.0002
X1	0.0005	X2	0.0003	X1	-0.0007

10 Sensitivity analysis

10.1 Sensitivity analysis of parameter d

To test the robustness of our findings to the assumption of full recovery ($d=1$), we conducted a sensitivity analysis by varying the d parameter by $\pm 15\%$. We modeled a "Build Back Better" scenario with $d=0.85$ and an "Incomplete Recovery" scenario with $d=1.15$. The analysis was performed for all cities across the 2019-2022 period.

Figure S6 illustrates the conceptual difference between these scenarios using the recovery curves for Beijing (2019) as a representative example.

Fig. S6 Example recovery curves for Beijing (2019) under different d parameter scenarios.

The results of the sensitivity analysis show that the calculated metric values are highly correlated between the baseline and the alternative scenarios. **Figure S7** presents the Spearman rank correlation analysis for the Resilience metric values. The high correlation coefficients ($\rho = 0.976$ and $\rho = 0.807$, respectively) indicate that the calculated resilience scores are not highly sensitive to the final recovery assumption.

This confirms that cities identified as having high or low resilience in our primary analysis would largely maintain their relative standing, making our conclusions about spatial patterns robust.

Fig. S7 Correlation of resilience scores between baseline and sensitivity scenarios.

Similarly, **Figure S8** shows a strong positive correlation for the time-based metrics. This confirms that cities that recover quickly in the baseline scenario also tend to recover or stabilize quickly in the alternative scenarios, reinforcing the stability of our findings.

Fig. S8 Correlation of Time-Based Metrics between Baseline and Sensitivity Scenarios.

10.2 Sensitivity analysis of function forms

To better justify our choice of functional form, we have expanded our discussion in the manuscript to clarify the selection process. We considered three plausible functions to model the time-dependent recovery component, $f(t|b,c)$:

- **Exponential form (baseline):** $f(t|b,c) = \exp[-ct^b]$. This form is widely used in resilience literature for its flexibility and its basis in the gamma distribution, which provides strong theoretical properties like asymptotic stability and quasi-convexity.
- **Power-law form (alternative):** $f(t|b,c) = 1/(ct^b + 1)$. This form models a recovery process with a "long tail," where the final stages of recovery can be significantly prolonged.
- **Logarithmic form (alternative):** $f(t|b,c) = 1/\ln(ct^b + e)$. This form represents an initially very rapid recovery that decelerates sharply over time.

Figure S9 depicts the recovery paths of three functions in Beijing in 2019, with the horizontal axis spanning 365 days. The characteristics of the three functions are evident. Clearly, against the backdrop of China's nationwide disaster relief efforts, the impact of a rainstorm disaster should be quickly recovered (Tang et al. 2019; Zhuang et al. 2024). The exponential form is more suitable for the study of disaster recovery.

Fig. S9 Comparison of recovery functions for Beijing (2019).

We compared the baseline Exponential recovery function with two common alternatives: a Power-Law form and a Logarithmic form. The results show that the resilience metric is highly robust to this choice. As shown in **Fig. S10**, the resilience scores generated by the alternative functions are strongly correlated with the baseline results ($\rho = 0.962$ for Power Law and $\rho = 0.823$ for Logarithmic).

Fig. S10 Correlation of Resilience Scores with Alternative Functional Forms.

However, the analysis of recovery time reveals significant differences (**Fig. S11**). Both the Power-Law and Logarithmic functions exhibit much slower recovery dynamics, with many cities failing to reach their pre-disaster performance level even after 1000 days. This indicates that these functional forms are less suitable for modeling the relatively rapid recovery process that is the focus of this study, though they may be applicable for longer-term reconstruction studies. This finding strongly justifies the selection of the Exponential form as the most appropriate model for our analysis.

Fig. S11 Correlation of Recovery Time with Alternative Functional Forms.

10.3 Sensitivity analysis of resilience time boundary

The 30-day integration boundary (T) used to calculate the final resilience score was varied by $\pm 15\%$ ($T=25.5$ and $T=34.5$). **Figure S12** illustrates how this change in the integration window affects the calculated resilience area for a single recovery curve.

The figure shows a single recovery curve, with the shaded areas representing the calculated resilience (area under the curve) for each of the three integration time boundaries.

The analysis confirms that this assumption does not affect the study's conclusions. While the absolute resilience scores scale linearly with the time boundary, the Spearman rank correlation of the scores between the baseline (T=30) and the alternative scenarios is perfect ($\rho = 1.000$), as shown in **Fig. S13**. This indicates that the relative performance of cities is perfectly preserved.

Fig. S12 Illustration of resilience calculation with different time boundaries for Beijing (2019).

Fig. S13 Correlation of resilience scores with varied time boundaries.

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